

German Committee for Research
with Synchrotron Radiation

Research with Photons

Light for the Future

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Perspectives

German Committee for Research with Synchrotron Radiation

Synchrotron radiation is the light that gives us a better understanding of the material world.

These photons provide insight into the microscopic structure of materials and the relationship between structure and function. This knowledge is essential for tackling the key challenges of our time, such as the generation of clean and affordable energy, protecting the environment, improving health and well-being, as well as information and data science where tailored materials are at the heart of a sustainable future.

Synchrotron radiation is extremely brilliant electromagnetic radiation reaching all the way from the far infrared to the X-ray regime. It is generated at large-scale research facilities, such as storage rings or free-electron lasers, where charged particles, accelerated to almost the speed of light, emit highly brilliant and intense radiation.

The broad spectrum of applications provides unique insight into materials, living matter, and the processes they are subjected to. This renders synchrotron radiation indispensable both for fundamental research and applied science. Owing to a world class portfolio of outstanding radiation sources, German research with synchrotron radiation is world-leading and researchers in Germany are fully embedded in the national and international research landscape. This leading position should be strengthened by the continuing successful collaboration between Helmholtz Centers, universities, and other research organisations, facilitated e.g. by the action plan „ErUM-Pro“ of the Federal Ministry for Education and Research (BMBF).

The German Committee for Research with Synchrotron Radiation (KFS) is the elected body to represent the synchrotron radiation user community in Germany and at international institutions with German participation. The KFS provides a framework for the German photon science community to help shape the future of the field. In order to quantify the needs of the broad and diverse user community, the KFS recently conducted a survey, the results of which are integrated into the recommendations presented here.

The German KFS represents an interdisciplinary community using a broad range of techniques. The common denominator is the need for world class sources for top-level research. The upgrade programmes for the radiation sources (PETRA IV, BESSY III) are the best path into the future.

Recommendations

Solving challenges

A fundamental understanding of matter and functional materials is the basis for solving the great challenges of our time. Therefore, the KFS sees the need to provide a broad range of synchrotron radiation methods. p. 4, 22

Developing sources

Germany has a leading role in synchrotron radiation based research. To maintain this position, the KFS recommends investing in further development of the synchrotron radiation sources. The KFS therefore supports the projects PETRA IV and BESSY III. p. 6/8

Advancing digitalisation

The KFS sees great potential in strategies for data management, analysis, storage and availability. The dialogue initiated in preparation for the BMBF's ErUM-Data action plan and with other funding agencies should be continued and deepened. p. 18

Strengthening innovation

The KFS recommends that co-operation with industry should be further strengthened. The framework for this can be created through more automation, special sample environments, by strengthening expertise at universities and tools and databases freely available at the synchrotron radiation sources. p. 14

Attracting bright minds

Embedding universities in synchrotron-based research enables the training of next-generation specialists and managers at the highest level. It is the opinion of the KFS that academic career paths based on the use of synchrotron radiation should be attractive and plannable. p. 16

Involving users

Excellent researchers with an active scientific network are the driving force in synchrotron science. The successful and close integration of the user community with radiation sources should be further intensified and structurally promoted. p. 12

Research

on a broad basis

Basic research bears applied fruits.
The large scale facilities are an ideal nurturing ground.

“Synchrotron radiation enables a very broad spectrum of scientific research - ranging from basic research in physics and the life sciences to the analysis of art and cultural artefacts. Basic research provides the understanding of the structure, dynamics and interaction of matter that we need to shape our living environment. Thus, fundamental findings can bear unexpected fruitful applications.”

PD Dr. Bridget M. Murphy, CAU Kiel
Chair of the 11. KFS

“Application-oriented questions are as much in the focus of research with synchrotron radiation as fundamental research. A few examples: Structural elucidation of biochemical processes for the development of new pharmaceuticals, the development of catalysts for more efficient chemical processes and the production of sustainable fuels or materials for solar panels - in all cases important future topics. This is only possible with excellent instrumentation and a suitable infrastructure.”

Prof. Dr. Jan-Dierk Grunwaldt, KIT Karlsruhe
Vice chair of the 11. KFS

“Research with photons at large research facilities now generates huge amounts of data. Evaluating and archiving these data streams and making the results available to all researchers and the public in databases are current challenges for us. Here, we as users have to cooperate intensively with the research institutions in order to create a modern research data management system. **In this way, digitalisation can really transform our scientific work**”.

Prof. Dr. Christian Gutt, Universität Siegen
KFS Portfolio Instrumentation and Data Management

Requirements

Infrastructure for research

Synchrotron radiation offers unique possibilities to researchers. Its high intensity over a broad energy range allows experiments, which are not possible in a normal laboratory. Germany hosts several excellent synchrotron facilities. In order to stay competitive on the international level, continuous modernization programmes for hardware and software are necessary. Also, optimal beam parameters and modern infrastructure are essential.

What do we need for future research?

Infrastructure

We need dedicated laboratory facilities for experiments under realistic conditions and with complementary methods along with setups for automated measurements.

Wavelength

Different areas of research require not only distinct but also variable wavelength/photon energy ranges.

Resolution

In nature, processes occur on different time and length scales. Therefore, methods and measuring equipment covering the smallest detail up to the 'big picture' - both spatially and temporally - are needed.

Intensity

The highest possible intensity is required to enable real-time studies on smallest volumes with tailored X-ray beams which allow us to follow processes in real time.

Coherence

In order to study the smallest objects and their properties, the laser-like coherence of the synchrotron radiation is needed.

Complementary Sources

This complex field of parameters can only be covered by a suite of complementary synchrotron radiation sources.

Synchrotron sources

Basis of research

Staying at the top

Germany is one of the world leaders in research with synchrotron radiation. Researchers use synchrotron radiation for basic research and applications on the one hand and for further developing sources and methods on the other. Most sources worldwide are upgrading to multibend achromatic storage ring technology with much finer bundling of the electron bunches. In order to maintain their leading position, German sources also require upgrading in the near future. The following points should be pursued in the process:

- First-class infrastructure
- Wide range of applications
- Complementary sources
- Qualified user support
- Educating the next generation

The successful implementation of these points should be achieved through participation of the universities in the

development of instrumentation (ErUM-Pro). Naturally, the contribution of the Helmholtz Centres and other non-university research institutes is of great importance.

BESSY II at HZB (Berlin) is a third-generation 1.7 GeV ring source focusing on soft and medium-energy X-rays.

Currently **PETRA III** at DESY (Hamburg) is one of the world's most brilliant ring sources producing high-energy photons.

Thanks to the superconducting accelerator technology, **FLASH** at DESY is still the only free-electron laser (FEL) covering the ultraviolet and soft X-ray range at a high repetition rate even after 15 years of operation.

The **ESRF** (Grenoble, France) is Europe's leading synchrotron radiation source. Twenty-five years ago it was the first third-generation source, and since 2020 ESRF-EBS, a fourth-generation source, is now in operation. With a focus on high-energy and nano-focused radiation, its capabilities go beyond those of the national synchrotron sources.

Since 2017, the **European XFEL** (Hamburg/Schenefeld) has been generating ultra-short, coherent and intense X-ray FEL pulses for the study of the dynamics of atomic and electronic structure. First experiments have revealed possibilities for research that represent a quantum leap for science with photons.

Smaller radiation sources such as **DELTA** (Dortmund), **KARA** (Karlsruhe) and **ELBE** (Dresden) play an important role due to their easier availability and specialized instrumentation - not least for training and industry.

Future projects

Hit the diffraction limit

DESY is planning the new source **PETRA IV** with ultra-small emittance, which is expected to reach the physical limits in terms of smallest achievable source size of synchrotron radiation in the range of energies of about 10 keV. This unique gain in brilliance would make **PETRA IV** the ultimate X-ray microscope for the observation of chemical and physical processes from atoms to visible objects on a time scale ranging from nanoseconds to hours.

Soft, but extremely brilliant

The successor source **BESSY III** will create completely new analytical capabilities. The research facility will focus on soft and medium X-rays and on in-situ and operando spectroscopy and microscopy methods. Highest beam stability and unique spatial, spectral and temporal resolution will be the key parameters of this new source.

KFS recommendations

The future projects of the radiation sources are the right way into the future of research with synchrotron radiation. **PETRA IV** and **BESSY III** will cover different parameter ranges. Their multi-bend-achromat lattice technology will allow completely new types of experiments. At the FELs, the development is moving towards fully coherent X-ray pulses. We need these new sources for a profound understanding of matter.

The user-friendliness of the instruments for industry and research should be further improved in the course of the upgrade programmes, also by means of increasing digitalisation of the infrastructure.

The KFS explicitly supports the plans for the new radiation sources **BESSY III** and **PETRA IV**, as well as **FLASH2020+** and the expansion of the European XFEL.

FLASH and European XFEL

Developments in superconducting FELs are moving towards extremely short attosecond photon pulses with properties similar to those of optical lasers due to seeding, as well as a flex-

ible combination of FELs and lasers of various wavelengths, and in the medium term also towards so-called continuous wave (cw) operation. Upgrade programmes are planned for **FLASH** and

the European XFEL to realise many of the aspects mentioned before in accordance with the wishes of the broad user community.

Top research needs top sources.

Sources with complementary beam properties offer the user community the required broad spectrum of methods.

Research with photons

in numbers (per year in Germany)

The numbers here are typical annual averages. They have been carefully collected, but are nevertheless to be understood as estimates.

2000

participants of user meetings at the facilities

Total of 9 sources in Germany or with German partnership, thereof

7 facilities with user operation

21 sources in Europe, 60 across the world

from 25 companies, 85 universities, 115 research institutions

4000
users

3000 experiments

28 PB
(28×10^{15} bytes)
data

1500 publications

150 patents
in Europe

User community

Interdisciplinary requirements

Broad spectrum

Research from physics, chemistry and biology, medicine, engineering and geosciences to research on art and cultural assets requires a wide variety of X-ray methods. The user community of synchrotron and FEL sources encompasses a very broad spectrum of scientific research, as a recent survey by the KFS explicitly showed.

Societal challenges

Due to its diversity, our research addresses important social issues including energy conversion, storage and use, health, information technology, as well as climate and environmental protection. A deeper understanding of the properties of matter forms the basis.

User community

The largest proportion of the user community is located at universities and state research institutions. Industry also makes use of the unique research opportunities at synchrotron sources, but often remains invisible to the public due to the confidential nature of the results.

Changing needs

The methodological demands on the sources also reflect this diversity. The KFS survey shows: In the future, dynamic measurements on complex objects in operation and in real time will play an even greater role than at present. For medical and biological research, high-resolution imaging techniques and automated experiments are of particular importance. Together, they create the growing need for data management in the user community.

Sources are the basis

Availability and further development of the synchrotron and FEL sources in their bandwidth is essential for this diverse user community. Through their infrastructure, the centres provide the only possibility for a substantial part of the user community to pursue their research questions.

Internationality

Science at large-scale research facilities is particularly internationally oriented. At present, 40% of the users of German synchrotrons and FELs come from abroad - and researchers from Germany experiment in other countries. Excellent science can thus build bridges and open dialogues where political contacts have become demanding.

Topic

Scientific field

Studied systems

The results of the 2019 KFS survey clearly show the broad range of research with synchrotron radiation: researchers from all natural science areas are searching for answers to questions concerning materials, energy, technology, health and information. The trend is to investigate real processes in real time.

The KFS recommends that the successful, close cooperation of researchers at universities and other research institutions with the sources continue to be funded intensively and structurally.

„The questions and needs within the user community are very diverse. This concerns both technical requirements and the service at the research institutions. Some have their own expertise and others need full support for experimentation. As the contact person for user issues in the KFS, I try to keep an eye on all of them and include them in the strategy discussion.“

Prof. Dr. Birgit Kanngießer, TU Berlin
KFS Portfolio of User Affairs

Innovation

Rewards of research

Long-standing tradition

The use of synchrotron radiation in industry has a long-standing tradition. Over many decades it has proven to be a valuable, practical and reliable tool. The fields of application range from physics, analytics or chemistry to biology and pharmacy. Around one hundred publications per year underline the tremendous interest shown by industry in large-scale research facilities - an attractive opportunity for Germany as a business location.

Cooperation and service for success

In order to overcome the hurdles for companies, cooperation between large-scale facilities, companies, research institutions and universities needs to be strengthened. Industrial use that does not take place within the framework of cooperations is particularly dependent on service on-site at the sources. Also automated measurements are very important. In the coming years, such opportunities should be systematically expanded and customised to relevant applications.

Companies benefit from:

Basic understanding

Fundamental knowledge is the driver for creativity and enables knowledge-based design of pharmaceuticals, catalysts, functional materials, etc.

Spin-offs

New technology is created in the design and construction of synchrotron equipment, e.g. production facilities, mirrors or new detectors.

Recruitment of talented scientists

Companies recruit young, highly qualified graduates who preferably have experience and training in an interdisciplinary work environment.

Potential through upgrades

The new methods created by upgrades or improved detectors allow a much deeper insight. Some functional materials can only be understood by "watching" them at work. This opens up new fields of research and application.

Examples of companies

From the approximately 300 companies using German sources, that have been involved in research with synchrotron radiation visible by means of publications, participation in workshops or patents, some examples are listed below:

- Airbus Operations GmbH (aircraft technology)
- AstraZeneca (pharmaceuticals)
- BASF AG (chemical industry)
- Carl Zeiss AG (optics, semiconductor technology)
- Dassault Systemes Deutschland GmbH (software)
- Volkswagen AG (automobiles)

"Research with synchrotron radiation is an important tool for us to improve our products. In the development of lightweight materials for electromobility, we benefit from non-destructive investigations under real conditions that are only possible at the synchrotron. The cooperation with experts in science opens up new possibilities for us."

Dr. Astrid Wollenberg
Volkswagen Group Innovation
Center of Innovation | Battery and Materials
Head of Metals

The KFS recommends the following measures:

Strengthening capabilities

- Extension of research and data infrastructure
- Promoting start-ups
- Initiating projects between sources, researchers and industry

Facilitating industrial research

- Deepening cooperation
- Strengthening service
- Extending remote access
- Enabling rapid access

Encouraging application

- Organizing workshops on specialised topics
- Initiating lighthouse projects
- Involving the user community

Young talent

Young researchers of today are the future of science

Career development

Research for a better world needs young investigators. Science with photons at large-scale research facilities creates a pool of talent for the next generation in universities and industry. In Germany in particular, universities and therefore PhD students and postdocs are strongly involved in method development at photon sources through BMBF funding programmes. Thereby, young researchers receive a unique training in how to both design and execute experiments and evaluate data and write publications. Additionally they learn how to develop innovative hardware and software solutions. The opportunity to assume

From the perspective of the KFS, academic career paths based on the use of synchrotron radiation should be attractive and plannable.

responsibility for novel experiments at an early stage in an interdisciplinary environment is the perfect preparation for leading positions in science and industry.

International networking

Summer schools and conferences organized by the KFS together with the Committee Research with Neutrons (KFN), the photon and neutron sources and the universities are particularly attractive to young scientists. These events combine basic research and application, and create excellent international networking opportunities for doctoral students and postdocs.

Bright minds for research

Clear career paths and successful support programmes are the key to attracting the best talents for a scientific career after the postdoc phase. The combination of cutting-edge research questions, excellent

infrastructure and diverse funding opportunities is ideal for setting up junior research groups. The BMBF's open programmes promote close cooperation between universities and research centers. This also allows the latest scientific methods to be quickly integrated into university study programmes. Internships and experiments at the large-scale research facilities motivate students at the various levels of education.

Generation change

It is very important for the future that expertise in instrument development is passed on from the current to the next generation of users, as a generation change is imminent.

"As a student, exciting measurement campaigns with synchrotron radiation in Europe and the USA attracted me to heterogeneous catalysis. During my diploma and doctoral theses, I expanded this work together with partners from industry, such as Umicore GmbH. The responsibility in these projects, which closely linked basic research with technical application, was fascinating and is a good basis for my new tasks and challenges at Audi AG today."

Dr. Andreas Gänzler, Audi AG

"The conversion of light to electricity in semiconductors is determined by excitons - bound electron-hole pairs. They move unimaginably fast and on extremely small length scales. That's why the ultrafast X-ray flashes of an X-ray laser are the perfect way to see the movement of excitons. A precise understanding of these processes is the prerequisite for the development of new efficient energy materials. In my research group, which I am currently setting up as part of a Freigeist Fellowship from the Volkswagen Foundation, I intend to push the limits of what is possible."

Dr. Daria Gorelova, Universität Hamburg

"During my PhD, by combining measurements at BESSY with time-resolved experiments on a laser-driven soft X-ray light source at the MBI, I was able to investigate the reaction of magnetic systems to ultra-short light pulses. Synchrotron radiation also plays a key role in my current research on magnetically ordered materials, because it enables me to observe the atomic subsystems in complex samples separately."

Dr. Felix Willems, Max-Born-Institut Berlin

Digital opportunities and challenges

Data for science

The quantity of data is increasing rapidly in the synchrotron and FEL radiation science area, due to improved source brilliance and development of fast 2D X-ray detectors. The data rates of modern detectors range from a few GB/second up to 100 GB/second.

Added value

At the same time, digitalisation is rapidly gaining importance for areas such as modeling, simulation, for example with digital twins, data management, automated data analysis, machine learning methods and artificial intelligence.

KFS recommendations

The KFS has identified the digitalisation needs together with the user community in a series of events and a proposal was submitted for the NFDI programme. In addition, a White Paper describing required measures for the next ten years was submitted to the BMBF in collaboration with user representatives from other science areas at large-scale research facilities. The proposed measures range from a tenure-track programme for junior professorships to hardware and include the application of artificial intelligence and machine learning for the analysis of extremely large amounts of data.

Progress through implementation

The implementation of these recommendations through the BMBF's ErUM-Data action plan and in coordination with our European partners and other projects, such as the national research data infrastructure, remains a challenge for the coming years, which the KFS will continue to support.

Important topics for the digital future

- Guidelines:
- FAIR principle (see box left), metadata standards
- Amount of data: Increasing data rates
- Standard formats
- Evaluation on the fly
- Data reduction
- Data from "intelligent experiments"
- State-of-the-art analytics
- Archiving, databases and curation.

"The introduction of FAIR principles, in particular the development of standards for data formats and metadata, will significantly accelerate the routine use of research with photons. Especially users from other disciplines will benefit from the easier access to data. This opening to a broader user community is an invitation to our partners in industry to exploit the potential of synchrotron radiation: FAIR principles represent uniform, standardized data access."

Dr. Alexander Rack, ESRF (Grenoble)

"As a frequent user of synchrotron radiation, I find that handling and treatment of experimental data is one of the greatest challenges. Datasets are not only increasing in size but also in complexity. As a community, we could benefit greatly from innovative methods, such as machine learning and artificial intelligence, for data evaluation. It is important that the KFS promotes this concern at national and international level."

Dr. Thomas Sheppard, KIT (Karlsruhe)

KFS recommends the implementation of the FAIR Principles.

Data should be:

- Findable
- Accessible
- Interoperable
- Reusable

New digital approaches will improve research and have an impact on society. The KFS recommends that the necessary measures are funded. Above all, human resources are crucial.

Live research

from ideas to results

Modern medicine

Controlling membranes

Svenja Hövelmann, Master's student at Kiel University, is investigating basic mechanisms of drug transport into human cells.

Preparation in the lab

Before she and her colleague Jonas Warias can measure at P08, PETRA III at DESY (see photo below) how the layer thickness and the lateral structure of a cell membrane changes when certain azobenzene glycolipids are switched

by light, she has to thoroughly prepare for the measurement campaign at home in the laboratory.

Characterization

She uses a Langmuir-trough to investigate phase transitions of her membrane-forming phospholipids in order to characterise her freshly prepared sample before it is measured at the synchrotron.

Key to success

„It's all about preparation - measurement time is requested long in advance and cannot be extended if problems pop up," says Svenja Hövelmann.

Ant fossil

In amber

An ant trapped in amber 53 million years ago was the topic investigated by an international research team on the ESRF's ID20 instrument, on the other hand, focused more on measurement, as the sample has been kindly prepared by nature in a rather durable state.

Organic carbon

„We use 3D X-ray Raman imaging to determine the chemical composition. We had developed this method over four years - from the experi-

mental setup to the software. The burning question here was whether we could detect organic carbon in an amber matrix," says Dr. Christoph Sahle, instrument scientist at ID20, see photos above.

Experiment

Following two weeks of final preparation at the beamline, the actual measurement lasted just 12 hours. „What was particularly exciting was the interdisciplinary work with experts from very different research areas," says Christoph Sahle. „Our results were published in Science Advances," he adds smiling.

Magnetic materials

Large amounts of data

Even during his experiment at the European XFEL with Dr. David Lomidze, Prof. Dr. Stefano Bonetti (Stockholm University / Ca' Foscari University of Venice) was busy with evaluation, see photo below. „400 terabytes of experimental data are a great challenge," says Stefano Bonetti. „The analysis of the large amounts of data requires powerful computing along with efficient and structured data management."

Magnetic memory

The goal of their research is to increase the efficiency of magnetic data storage. To this end, extremely fast processes in quantum materials with the highest spatial resolution are investigated at the SCS instrument.

Evaluation

The data is compressed and analysed so that a real image of the sample is visible at different points in time. Data analysis is the most time-consuming part of this research and it takes several months to a year to reach final conclusions.

Research fields

Examples from research

Materials

From structure to properties

Structure is the key

Materials Research

The discovery of X-ray diffraction by Laue, Friedrich and Knipping in 1912 can be seen as the starting point of modern materials science on the atomic level. X-ray diffraction reveals the 3D structure of materials, which is determined by the periodic arrangement of atoms in the crystal lattice. Physical properties of materials such as rigidity, thermal and electrical properties etc. are closely linked to the crystallographic structure. Therefore, understanding structure-property relations is a key in the search for new materials with tailored properties.

Composite structures

Real structure

Most technical materials are composites, i.e. they are composed of microscopically small grains of different crystallographic phases and orientation. Although the grain structure can be visualized using light microscopes, real structure determination requires the use of synchrotron radiation. Beamlines delivering X-ray radiation, focused down to a spot size of 100 nm and even smaller, allow the analysis of single grains. X-ray energies up to 100 keV give access to grains located deep inside the bulk of the material, which is impossible with visible light.

Understanding fractures

Material fatigue

The importance of structure analysis becomes clear when considering the ICE derailment at Enschede in 1998. The cause of this German rail disaster was a fatigue crack in a single wheel tyre. Such wheel tyres are made of duplex steel, consisting of micron-sized grains of ferrite and austenite, two crystallographic phases of iron. In the course of cyclic loading, dislocation networks are formed in austenite, creating high stress at the interfaces towards ferrite grains. As a result of this tension, micro-cracks appeared in the much more brittle ferrite, which ultimately led to fracture. Stress and microcrack formation at the ferrite to austenite interfaces as function of cyclic load could be clarified using micro-focussed X-ray radiation at the ESRF.

Learning from spider silk

Bionic materials

Spider silk is a natural, biodegradable material with mechanical properties far superior to man-made fibres. Using synchrotron radiation, the response of the structure of these protein fibres to mechanical stress was investigated. It was shown that the arrangement of the proteins in the thread is even more important than their chemical composition. This understanding on a molecular level has paved the way for the development of artificial spider silk, which is now being produced industrially. The first applications range from cosmetics to medical products, clothes and light building materials. The potential of bionic materials points far beyond this.

Water is exceptional

Decoding dynamics

Water is the basis of all life. Biological processes cannot function without water. In the cells of living organisms, proteins work in a liquid environment. In oceans, rivers and glaciers, water shapes our planet and its climate - and water is essential for current and future technologies. Hydrogen, for example, has great potential as an energy carrier and can in principle be produced directly from water and sunlight with the aid of a suitable catalyst. Nevertheless, many extraordinary properties of this unique substance are still not understood in detail. To understand them, researchers must decipher the complex interplay between the structure and dynamics of water molecules.

Health

Molecular structures and processes

Understanding biomolecules

Structural biology

Today's understanding of life at the molecular and atomic level would not have been achieved without X-ray crystallography, involving in particular synchrotron sources. It all started in 1958 with the elucidation of the first structure of a biological macromolecule: The oxygen-binding protein myoglobin was decoded in 1958. In the following decades, ever more complex macromolecules and even the structure of complete viruses were deciphered using this method. Very recently, the structure of the main protease of the causative agent of COVID-19 was determined at BESSY II allowing the development of a suitable inhibitor, an important step on the way to a drug against SARS-CoV-2.

Protein Data Bank

The enormous wealth of information of all these structures is archived in the Protein Data Bank and an analysis of the structures archived there (~161,000 entries at present) reflects the importance of synchrotron radiation. Almost 90% of the deposited structures were determined by X-ray crystallography with the overwhelming majority of these structures relying on the high brilliance of synchrotron sources. At the same time, the tunable wavelength at these sources allowed the development of new approaches to solve the phase problem.

New synchrotron sources

The new and planned light sources (European XFEL, ESRF EBS, PETRA IV and BESSY III) will allow the analysis of ever smaller crystals with the ultimate goal of visualizing individual macromolecules. Serial crystallographic methods are increasingly being used. The extremely short pulses of the free-electron laser sources (upgrade to cw operation) will allow monitoring of chemical reactions with high spatial and temporal resolution.

Developing novel drugs

Rational drug design

The three-dimensional structures of surface receptors and enzymes are ideal starting points for the development of new pharmaceuticals. Rational drug design is an iterative process involving an intense interplay between structural biologists, pharmacologists as well as theoretical and synthetic chemists. Based on the three-dimensional structure of a protein in complex with a low-molecular weight compound, this starting ligand is optimized until a high-affinity drug candidate has been generated.

Inhibiting enzymes

FEL X-ray pulses have recently paved the way for the targeted development of drugs against African sleeping sickness. Hope rests on blocking an enzyme that is vital for the causative parasite *Trypanosoma brucei*. The structure of the enzyme has now been deciphered with great accuracy, so that one can use rational drug design to construct an inhibitor that specifically binds to this enzyme and thus inhibits proliferation of the pathogen. This approach is also promising for the fight against other parasites.

Mapping the brain

Grasping Alzheimer's

A better understanding of the microscopic structure of the brain can help to fight diseases such as multiple sclerosis or Alzheimer's disease, in which morphological changes in the neuronal architecture occur. X-ray tomography, also known as computer tomography (CT), is pretty much the only way to visualize intact biomedical samples without preparing thin tissue slices. At today's synchrotron radiation sources, individual nerve cells can be resolved. At the planned, extremely brilliant sources, one could even visualize their connection points and thus the entire network architecture of the brain.

Information on atomic length scales

Technological insight

Information age

Microelectronics turned into nanoelectronics – many years of research with synchrotron radiation have led to miniaturisation of semiconductor chips as they can now be written with soft X-ray radiation. We have reached the scale where we require control over single atoms and need to understand their quantum properties to further improve performance. It is not just about shrinking systems - instead we have to search for entirely new effects and methods allowing us to process and store data faster and more efficiently than today.

Quantum world

In the future, will we compute not just using electrons but also via spin currents and light pulses? Will we be able to process information more efficiently and thus save energy? The use of quantum effects in computers is in its infancy, with huge potential for future applications. Modern, brilliant synchrotron radiation sources are key instruments for the future development of information technology: They provide an atomic resolution view on increasingly smaller systems and faster processes, zooming into the quantum world.

Materials for nano-electronics

High performance electronics

To maintain the trend towards higher performance electronic devices such as smartphones or computers, new concepts and materials beyond the classic semiconductor silicon are required. One of the most promising platforms are quantum materials. Here, the interaction between myriads of electrons generates a huge variety of exotic properties. Synchrotron- and FEL-radiation enable us to record movies of these “dancing electrons” in real time. Such studies lay the foundation for smaller, faster and more efficient devices, for quantum computers featuring tremendous computing power or for superconductors which can transport current without losses under realistic conditions.

Storing information

Electronics, photonics, spintronics – what is the next step?

Electronic methods for data transfer have long been important, but increasingly data is transmitted with light and stored in small magnetic structures. In order to improve information technology, it is important not only to develop existing concepts but also to search for entirely new approaches.

In the field of spintronics, for example, researchers investigate how the spin of an electron instead of its charge can be used as the elementary unit for computation. Combining this approach with new functional materials promises an increase of both performance and efficiency.

The integration of spintronics with light-driven manipulation of information is a good example. The ultrashort X-ray flashes generated in synchrotron radiation sources and X-ray lasers are an indispensable tool in this research.

They enable us to understand the extremely fast processes involved.

Novel data storage devices

Due to the explosion of data use in society, there is now a need to store tremendous amounts of data. “Big data” does not float in a cloud, but is physically stored on hard drives in large data centres.

Up to now, research with synchrotron radiation has helped to increase the storage density continuously: Today, a single bit on a hard disk drive is only about 40 nm x 15 nm x 15 nm in size! Researchers work on making even smaller structures. Constructing novel data storage architectures with magnetic skyrmions allows data storage and moving and writing bits via current

pulses rather than magnetic fields. X-rays from synchrotron radiation sources and free-electron lasers make it possible to quantify and image the magnetization of extremely small structures, thus contributing enormously to future research in this field.

Energy and environment

Efficient processes and energy carriers

Rational design

New possibilities

Watching real processes at work ("operando") has become increasingly possible with recent advances

in synchrotron radiation. Beginning with X-ray absorption spectroscopy, a large toolbox of methods for this purpose has been developed in recent years. For example, processes in the environment and in energy materials can be understood and rationally improved, e.g. the charging and discharging of batteries, the operation of semiconductors in photocell light absorption or the function of fuel cells, hydrogen production during the electrolysis of water, and energy-efficient processes in the chemical industry.

Catalysis live

Efficient processes

Today, 95 % of all chemical products are produced in an energy-efficient way and with low emissions using catalysts. These will continue to play a central role in the future, e.g. in the development of energy-saving processes or in the energy transition.

Operando methods

How can you watch catalysts at work? In recent years there has been enormous progress in operando methods. Higher intensities and specially developed monochromators accelerate the measurement of X-ray absorption spectra. Spatially resolved and X-ray microscopic measurements increasingly allow us to capture the entire structural diversity of catalysts under reaction conditions.

Example air purification

A classic application of catalysts is the treatment of exhaust gases. More than 60 % of all noble metals go into this sector - a major resource problem. Using the latest X-ray methods, it was recently shown that pollutants such as carbon monoxide or hydrocarbons can be removed more efficiently if they are treated alternately in an oxygen-rich and a reducing atmosphere, thus optimizing particle size. This principle can even be used to regenerate catalysts that have aged.

Batteries for the future

Understanding the mode of operation

Lithium-ion batteries are the best known high-performance batteries. The deep knowledge of their mode of operation gained by using the latest synchrotron radiation X-ray methods can increase their stability and lifetime. In addition, the element lithium needs to be replaced, and sodium-based batteries are a promising candidate. X-ray diffraction measurements have recently identified relevant phase transformations during charge and discharge cycles. These findings can be used to develop even more powerful batteries in the future.

Wind and solar energy

Storage capacity

Besides batteries, the electrolysis of water is very attractive for storing solar and wind energy. To understand the method of operation, model electrodes for the oxygen generation reaction have recently been studied in detail by surface diffraction. Thanks to the BMBF research programme in ErUM-Pro, a device could be developed for this purpose that examines structural changes in grazing incidence. In this way, university research and the excellent infrastructure of Helmholtz large-scale facilities come together and help to develop important future technologies.

Hydrogen as an energy source

Clean energy source

The only product in the conversion of hydrogen is water, whereby the energy can be retrieved from a fuel cell in the form of electricity. Although hydrogen-powered fuel cell cars or buses are in use already, the technology is not yet ready for the general market.

Scattering methods

By developing scattering methods using extremely high-energy X-rays, structural changes in electrodes for fuel cells and electrolytic hydrogen production can be monitored on the atomic scale - an important step on the way to more efficient fuel cells.

Conclusion

Preservation and progress

What does top quality research with synchrotron radiation in Germany require?

Solving challenges

The German Committee for Research with Synchrotron Radiation (KFS) is convinced that a wide range of experiments must be available to solve the major challenges facing our society. Researchers from all areas of the natural sciences have specific questions that only research with synchrotron radiation can answer. Many different experimental approaches are necessary to find the answers. This requires a broadly diversified portfolio of beamlines and complementary radiation sources.

Developing sources

The KFS expressly supports the plans for the new radiation sources PETRA IV and BESSY III, as well as FLASH2020+ and the expansion of the European XFEL. Our large-scale research facilities should continue to provide the infrastructure needed to meet the requirements of our users in the future and support the cooperation between universities and research institutions. This should lead to new experimental methods, but also preserve successful established methods.

Advancing digitalisation

The KFS recommends promoting digitalisation by allocating necessary resources. Research with synchrotron radiation is at the forefront of digitalisation due to the extraordinary quantities of data that are generated and evaluated. We are working on strategies to speed up evaluation, facilitate the exchange of data with the research community and provide further training for users. Our goal of making data freely available and usable ("Open Data") can be a model for society.

Strengthening innovation

We advocate strengthening cooperation with industry. Innovative research with synchrotron radiation offers enormous potential for technology transfer, e.g. in materials research and health. The current challenge is to bring universities, research institutes and industrial partners together for research with synchrotron radiation. Communication and tailored funding of cooperation may be a solution to this challenge.

Attracting bright minds

Scientific career paths must become more predictable and attractive. Only then can the young scientists of today take on the leading positions in society, industry and research of tomorrow. To this end, we advocate sustainable funding programmes that open up attractive career paths and make them easier to plan.

Involving users

In the future, as today, we need funding measures such as the very successful ErUM-Pro, which involves universities and other research institutes in instrumental and methodological advancement at large research facilities. Not only will both partners profit directly from this active exchange, but also the entire community of all of synchrotron radiation researchers.

PD Dr. Bridget Murphy, KFS chair
On behalf of the KFS

Glossary

- BESSY: Berlin electron storage ring at HZB
- BMBF: Federal Ministry of Education and Research
- CAU Kiel: Kiel University
- DELTA: Dortmund Electron Accelerator, TU Dortmund
- DESY: Deutsches Elektronen-Synchrotron, Hamburg
- ELBE: Center for High-power Radiation Sources at Helmholtz-Zentrum Dresden-Rossendorf
- ErUM: Research on Universe and Matter, framework programme of the BMBF
- ESRF: European Synchrotron Radiation Facility in Grenoble, France
- ESRF-EBS: Extremely Brilliant Source of the ESRF
- ESUO: European Synchrotron and FEL User Organisation
- EuXFEL: European X-Ray Free-Electron Laser, Hamburg / Schenefeld
- FAIR: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
- FEL: Free-Electron Laser (X-ray laser)
- FELBE: "FEL with high Brilliance and Low Emittance" at Helmholtz-Zentrum Dresden-Rossendorf
- FLASH: Free-electron laser in Hamburg at DESY
- FLASH2020+: Upgrade of the Free-electron laser in Hamburg at DESY
- HDF5: Hierarchical Data Format
- HZB: Helmholtz-Zentrum Berlin
- HZG: Helmholtz-Zentrum Geesthacht
- KARA: Karlsruhe Research Accelerator at KIT
- KFS: Committee for Research with Synchrotron Radiation, elected user representation
- KIT: Karlsruhe Institute of Technology
- NEXUS is a data format
- NMR: Nuclear Magnetic Resonance
- PB: Petabyte, 10^{15} Bytes
- PETRA: Positron-Elektron-Tandem-Ring-Anlage at DESY
- RACIRI: Summer School of Röntgen-Ångström-Cluster (RÅC) and Ioffe-Röntgen-Institut (IRI)

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The results of the KFS survey, in which almost 900 researchers participated in the end of 2018 and the beginning of 2019, are published on the KFS website at <https://www.sni-portal.de/en/files/kfs-user-survey-2018-2019>.

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